

Studies on Equilibria in Dimethylsulphoxide-Water and Formamide-Water Mixtures

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Studies on the equilibria for the reactions

have been determined spectrophotometrically in DMSO-water and formamide-water mixtures using the data previously reported for the reaction

The results have been interpreted in terms of solvent basicity, changes in the solvent structures and ion-solvent interactions. The utility of such studies in determining the free energy of transfer of cations have been stressed.

It has been widely known that the change in the ion-solvent interactions on the transfer of electrolytes from one solvent to other may be small but is sufficiently large to cause dramatic changes in chemical reactions.

In order to understand the role of solvents like DMSO and formamide on the different equilibrium reactions, attempts have been made to study the following equilibria

in DMSO-water and formamide-water mixtures. The results of our investigations for reaction (1) have already been reported^{1,2}. We report the results on reactions (2) and (3) in this communication.

Experimental

The purification of the solvents, and the determination of the compositions of the solvent mixtures and their dielectric constants have been reported earlier^{1,2}. Experimental details are also similar to those reported earlier⁴⁻⁶.

The absorption maxima of the ferrodin complex show almost similar properties in these solvents, only the oscillator strength of this complex changes in these solvents⁷ (Tables 1 and 2). It has been further observed that due to the high basicity of these organic solvents, a fairly high concentration of acid

(HClO₄) is to be added to avoid the hydrolysis of the complexes in these mixed solvents.

Under our experimental conditions, only Fe-bipy₃²⁺ was formed, and no Fe bipy²⁺ or Fe bipy₂²⁺ as observed by Kolthoff *et al.*⁸. We find that the mono-complex is formed only when Fe²⁺ is present in large excess compared to bipy but the complex is rapidly converted to Fe bipy₃²⁺.

The extinction coefficients (ϵ) of ferrodin were determined from the measurements of optical densities of solutions containing 10-20-fold excess of ligand to different concentrations of Fe²⁺ at 520, 522 and 530 nm as described earlier⁴. The ϵ in different percentages of mixed solvents are given in Tables 1 and 2.

For the determination of the stability constants, optical densities of solutions containing different concentrations of Fe²⁺ and bipyridine were measured at 520, 522 and 530 nm. The concentrations of the complex were calculated from optical density readings and extinction coefficient values at these wavelengths. The concentrations of the complex came out to be almost equal at these wavelengths. For the calculation of equilibrium constant for reaction (2), the average values of the complex obtained from measurements at three wavelengths were taken.

Optical density measurements were taken at 298 K with a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer.

TABLE 1—MOLAR EXTINCTION COEFFICIENTS OF FERRODIIN AND pK VALUES FOR REACTIONS (1), (2) AND (3) IN DMSO-WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

DMSO wt%	Mole fraction of DMSO	1/D $\times 10^3$	Molar extinction coefficients at			(1) pK_T	(2) pK_a	(3) pK
			520 nm	522 nm	530 nm			
0.0	0.000	1.27	—	—	—	4.47	4.12	17.58
10.9	0.027	1.28	8480 $\pm$ 40	8558 $\pm$ 50	8401 $\pm$ 35	4.19	3.97	16.55
21.5	0.060	1.30	8568 $\pm$ 38	8638 $\pm$ 45	8518 $\pm$ 30	4.01	4.12	16.15
32.0	0.098	1.31	8654 $\pm$ 45	8671 $\pm$ 40	8581 $\pm$ 45	3.84	3.93	15.45
42.8	0.144	1.32	8716 $\pm$ 50	8800 $\pm$ 50	8685 $\pm$ 45	3.71	4.87	15.80
52.4	0.202	1.35	8827 $\pm$ 50	8862 $\pm$ 45	8734 $\pm$ 43	3.42	4.82	15.08
62.2	0.280	1.39	8878 $\pm$ 45	8938 $\pm$ 50	8827 $\pm$ 45	3.14	5.07	14.45
71.9	0.371	1.45	8969 $\pm$ 50	9018 $\pm$ 50	8873 $\pm$ 45	2.69	6.11	14.18
81.5	0.508	1.55	8848 $\pm$ 40	8911 $\pm$ 45	8800 $\pm$ 40	2.27	7.01	13.82
90.8	0.692	1.72	8761 $\pm$ 35	8830 $\pm$ 45	8734 $\pm$ 40	2.19	7.41	13.98

TABLE 2—MOLAR EXTINCTION COEFFICIENTS OF FERRODIIN AND pK VALUES FOR REACTIONS (1), (2) AND (3) IN FORMAMIDE-WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

DMSO wt %	Mole fraction of formamide	1/D $\times 10^3$	Molar extinction coefficients at			(1) pK_T	(2) pK_a	(3) pK
			520 nm	522 nm	530 nm			
0.0	0.000	1.27	—	—	—	4.47	4.12	17.58
11.2	0.048	1.21	8400 $\pm$ 40	8456 $\pm$ 48	8393 $\pm$ 30	3.28	5.08	14.72
22.1	0.103	1.14	8490 $\pm$ 35	8553 $\pm$ 45	8401 $\pm$ 30	3.13	5.05	14.44
32.7	0.163	1.08	8560 $\pm$ 40	8610 $\pm$ 45	8513 $\pm$ 35	3.09	5.11	14.39
43.0	0.232	1.04	8650 $\pm$ 32	8700 $\pm$ 43	8581 $\pm$ 31	3.08	5.30	14.54
53.1	0.312	0.99	8733 $\pm$ 50	8833 $\pm$ 48	8633 $\pm$ 37	3.15	5.56	15.01
62.9	0.405	0.95	8800 $\pm$ 52	8830 $\pm$ 50	8671 $\pm$ 43	3.25	5.24	15.00
72.5	0.518	0.92	8863 $\pm$ 43	8600 $\pm$ 46	8490 $\pm$ 38	3.32	4.85	14.81
81.9	0.644	0.90	8843 $\pm$ 50	8900 $\pm$ 53	8827 $\pm$ 45	3.43	4.92	15.08
91.1	0.801	0.89	8761 $\pm$ 40	8850 $\pm$ 48	8731 $\pm$ 40	3.49	4.60	15.07

Results

The equilibrium constant for the reaction

$$K_a = \frac{C_{Fe^{2+}} \times C_{H^+}^2 \times f_{H^+}^2 \times f_{bipy^+}}{C_{Fe(bipy)_2^+} \times C_{H^+} \times f_{Fe(bipy)_2^+} \times f_{H^+}} \quad (4)$$

The present work has been carried out in solutions of ionic strengths, μ , of the order of (1.4-3.37) $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ where it is reasonable to assume $f_{Fe^{2+}} = f_{Fe(bipy)_2^+}$ and $f_{H^+} = f_{H^+}$. Moreover, the 'medium effects' of ions on the dissociation constants can only be ascertained if the work is carried out in very dilute solutions.

Now, $[H^+ bipy^+] = [bipy]_{total} - 3[Fe(bipy)_2^+] - [bipy]$ (5)

$$pK_T = B + \log U_H + \log \frac{[bipy H^+]}{[bipy]} \quad (6)$$

and $[Fe^{2+}]_{free} = [Fe^{2+}]_{total} - [Fe(bipy)_2^+]$ (7)

The $[H^+]$ values were calculated from pH meter readings $[B]$ after appropriate corrections⁸⁻¹². pK_T values have been reported⁸ previously.

The equilibrium constants for reaction (3) is

$$K = \frac{[Fe^{2+}][bipy]^2}{[Fe(bipy)_2^+]} = K_a \times K_T^2 \quad (8)$$

The equilibrium constants K_T , K_a and K in different percentages of DMSO-water and formamide-water mixtures are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Discussion

It has been found that extinction coefficient of the complexes are higher in mixed solvents and the trend is quite regular in DMSO-water. The extinction coefficient passes through a maximum at about 72 wt%. The trend, however, is somewhat different in formamide-water mixtures where two maxima are at about 63 and 82 wt% (Tables 1 and 2). These results could not be correlated with the solvent dielectric constant or other known solvent properties. However, since the extinction coefficients are related to the oscillator strengths, it is expected that the oscillator strengths would change with the change in solvent composition obviously due to change in solute-solvent interactions.

The results show the pK_a values for reaction (2) slightly decrease with the introduction of organic solvents but increase with increase in organic component. In case of DMSO-water, pK_a value passes through a minimum at about 30 wt% and then increases continuously but the pK_a -jump is very much conspicuous at about 82 wt% DMSO. In case of formamide-water, the pK_a value reaches a maximum at about 53 wt% and again at 82 wt% of formamide. It is thus apparent that $\Delta G^\ddagger$ values for reaction (2) are positive in most cases, i.e. the reaction is non-spontaneous in organic solvents mixtures. However, $\Delta G^\ddagger$ values for the reaction (3) are increasingly negative in DMSO-water indicating that reaction (3) is spontaneous, i.e. the dissociation of $Fe(bipy)_2^+$ is favoured in mixed solvents.

Similar conclusions may be derived in case of formamide-water. As in the case of reaction (2), significant changes are observed between 20-30 wt% of DMSO and in the region 43 to 53, and 82 wt% of formamide. The results indicate that Fe bipy_3^{2+} is less stable in these solvent mixtures but the stability is less in formamide-water mixtures. The reasons may be, (i) increase in basicity of the solvent mixtures and consequent removal of H^+ by the solvents, (ii) increase in solubility of bipyridine in the solvent mixtures, and (iii) competition of the solvents to form complexes with Fe^{2+} and consequent displacement of bipy by the solvents from Fe bipy_3^{2+} particularly when the DMSO or formamide concentrations are high.

All these reactions are isoelectric in character. Thus, the decrease in dielectric constant should have a slight effect on dissociation constants, the change in pK values must be due to solute-solvent interactions which are likely to be high in the solvent mixtures. The solvation of Fe bipy_3^{2+} and H bipy^+ should be less compared to those of Fe^{2+} and H^+ . It is expected that Fe^{2+} and H^+ would be preferentially solvated by water molecules. Displacement of H_2O by DMSO or formamide can occur only at high percentages of organic solvents.

It is seen that the pK_a values for reaction (2) is a linear function of $1/D$ at best upto 50 wt% beyond which considerable deviations arise. But it is impossible to get a clear idea of the solute-solvent interactions of the different ions in solutions.

In view of the inadequate knowledge of the solvational properties of ions in mixed solvents, nothing specific can be said. But it is apparent that the variation of the structural properties of the solvent systems, i.e. solvent-solvent and ion-solvent interactions are primarily responsible for the variation in pK values. In general, the addition of organic solvent to water first enhances the three-dimensional polymeric structure of water. Next, disruption of solvent structures (water, DMSO, formamide etc.) and formation of water-formamide or water-DMSO molecules take place. Ultimately at higher percentages, disruption of water-organic solvent bond and formation of ordered organic solvents take place due to dipole-dipole interactions and van der Waals force. Thus, the marked changes in the solvent structures take place at ~20-30 and 75-90 wt% of organic solvents. It is to be noted that in case of DMSO-water mixtures, unlike alcohol-water mixtures, maximum structure formation has been reported to be in the region of $X_{\text{DMSO}} \approx 0.35$ or higher^{13,14}. The changes in other physicochemical properties are also in the region $X_{\text{DMSO}} \approx 0.35$ to 0.50¹³⁻¹⁶.

Therefore, the solute-solvent interactions and solvent basicity would change and which would have

marked effects on the free energies of transfer in these regions.

But the most important aspect of the present study is to have the free energies of transfer, $\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{Fe}^{2+})$ from water to mixed solvents. For reaction (3), we have

$$\Delta G_f^\circ(3) = \Delta G_f^\circ(\text{Fe}^{2+}) + 3\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{bipy}) - \Delta G_f^\circ(\text{Fe bipy}_3^{2+}) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{or } \Delta G_f^\circ(\text{Fe}^{2+}) = \Delta G_f^\circ(3) - 3\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{bipy}) + \Delta G_f^\circ(\text{Fe bipy}_3^{2+}) \quad (10)$$

Thus, if we have the $\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{bipy})$ and $\Delta G_f^\circ[\text{Fe bipy}_3(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$ values from solubility measurements, $\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{Fe}^{2+})$ could be calculated. Since Fe^{2+} is present as perchlorates, use of $\Delta G_f^\circ[\text{Fe bipy}_3(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$ in equation (10) will obviously cancel $(\text{ClO}_4^-)_3$ from both sides^{17,18}. The method would thus form a valuable tool for determining the free energies of transfer of single ions, the importance and utility of which are well-known.

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References

1. B. G. COX and W. E. WAGHORNE, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1980, 9, 981.
2. C. C. DEB, D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1984.
3. C. C. DEB, D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1984.
4. D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 79, 885; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 787.
5. S. K. MAITY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 664.
6. A. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 697.
7. C. C. DEB, D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 284.
8. I. M. KOLTHOFF, D. L. LEUSSING and T. S. LEE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2173.
9. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. C. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
10. U. C. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1966, 50, 181.
11. S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 319.
12. R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH, Theory and Practice", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1973, p. 215.
13. J. KENTAMMA and J. J. LINDBERG, *Soumen Kemistilehti, B*, 1961, 33, 104.
14. J. M. OOWIE and P. M. JOFOROASKI, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, 39, 2240.
15. K. M. JUNG and J. B. PYNE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, 40, 3423.
16. H. B. SILVER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, 39, 8423.
17. D. SENGUPTA, A. PAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 2685.
18. A. BHATTACHARYYA, D. SENGUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1984, 265, 372.